

Improving the stiffness of high resolution DLP stereolithographic material

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Background

- Photo-polymerization of liquid resin is a highly flexible additive manufacturing technique in that material properties can be modulated by adding other ingredients.
- For example, the material may be made ferromagnetic or electrically conductive by adding magnetic or conductive particles to the resin.
- By adding reinforcing agents, the mechanical properties such as the Young's modulus of the resulting material can be enhanced.
- The effect of adding alumina particles and carbon nanotube into the resin to modify its modulus is examined.
- The resin is cured layerwise and the effect of layer thickness on the Young's modulus will also be studied.

Materials and method

- Resin: Photomer 4012/ Photomer 4017/ Photomer 4028.
- Carbon nanotube (CNT) and alumina particles are used as reinforcing agents.
- ACER P1500 DLP projector with the lens inverted to project a full size image of $4.3 \times 2.42 \text{ mm}^2$, with a pixel resolution of $2.2 \mu\text{m}$.
- Cantilever beams with dimensions $60 \mu\text{m} \times 60 \mu\text{m} \times 600 \mu\text{m}$ on a $0.1 \times 0.1 \times 0.1 \text{ mm}$ base is printed on a cover slip with layer thickness of $2 \mu\text{m}$, $3 \mu\text{m}$ and $5 \mu\text{m}$.
- Tested using a FEMTO TOOLS miniature load cell and a Solartron DFg1 LVDT.

Results

Effect of reinforcement on Stiffness

Effect of curing layer thickness on Stiffness

Conclusions

- Adding reinforcing agents such as alumina particles or carbon nanotube can significantly increase the stiffness of DLP stereolithographic material.
- With a curing layer thickness of $5 \mu\text{m}$, addition of $0.3 \text{ wt}\%$ of CNT raised the Young's modulus by $\sim 47\%$ while addition of $1 \text{ wt}\%$ of alumina particles increased it by 384% .
- Decreasing the curing layer thickness will also improve the Young's modulus. Without reinforcement, decreasing layer thickness from 5 to $2 \mu\text{m}$ raised modulus by 72% .
- With $0.3 \text{ wt}\%$ of CNT, decreasing layer thickness from 5 to $2 \mu\text{m}$ raised modulus by 284% . With $1 \text{ wt}\%$ of alumina, it increased by 340% .

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